

Healthcare Executives Hiring of Anesthesia Providers

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Background

- In California, Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNA) may practice as independent anesthesia providers at both inpatient and Ambulatory Surgery Centers (ASCs).
- It is unclear whether CRNAs are hired as independent anesthesia providers by Healthcare Executives (HCEs) in the vast number of free-standing ACS in California.
- The American Association of Nurse Anesthetists (AANA) set research priorities focused on gaining knowledge about HCEs' perceptions of CRNAs.
- Evidence-based research has shown there is no differences in patient safety outcomes based on the type anesthesia provider.

Purpose

- The purpose of this project was to explore HCEs' practices when hiring anesthesia providers and their perceptions about utilization of anesthesiologists versus Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNA).

Results

Anesthesia Provider Preference

➤ Most HCEs preferred to have an anesthesiologist present.

➤ Majority of HCEs (N=28) preferred to hire an anesthesiologist 17(53.1%) or a combination of anesthesiologist and CRNAs only 11 (34.4%); 15 (55.6%) were **not aware** of current state and federal regulations regarding CRNAs' independent scope of practice (SOP) in California.

HCEs Gap in Knowledge of CRNA SOP Laws

➤ Almost half (12, 44.4%) of respondents were **not aware** of malpractice court rulings that surgeons are not held more accountable when working with an independent CRNA or anesthesiologist.

Hiring Factors

➤ Additional factors HCEs use when considering hiring anesthesia providers. Safety was the most important factor when deciding on a provider, and educational background was the least important.

Method

- Qualtrics™ is an internet platform used to collect and analyze survey data.
- Survey consisted of 10 questions to explore HCEs' hiring practices and perceptions about CRNAs.

Setting

- Freestanding ASCs in California

Sample

- A convenience sample of self-identified HCEs. Three different lists of HCEs' email addresses were obtained and used to contact subjects. A total of 665 HCEs received the survey..
- Forty-four recipients opened the survey for a response rate of 6.6% with a final sample of 42

Recommendations

- Send representatives to the annual California Ambulatory Surgical Association (CASA) meeting to inform HCEs of CRNA SOP.
- Further research to be conducted on patients' perspective of care received by a CRNA. The results would be reported directly to the HCE at the ASC.